

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Report on the activities of OPERAS bodies

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Report on the activities of the OPERAS bodies

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Abstract

This report covers the activities of each of the tasks in OPERAS PLUS Work Package 3: Member States and Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders engagement for the reporting period September 2022 - December 2023 inclusive. In particular, it outlines OPERAS internal support to the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), Special Interest Groups (SIGs), Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), General Assembly (GA) and Executive Assembly (EA) in order to evidence effective engagement, quality and efficiency of internal communication and the coordination of the different internal groups of OPERAS.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

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Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AoC	OPERAS Assembly of the Commons
BGR	Board of Governing Representatives
COARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CO-OPERAS	OPERAS project which addressed the FAIR principles application challenges in the field of Social Sciences and Humanities
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication Project
EA	OPERAS Executive Assembly
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EQSIP	The Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing developed by DIAMAS
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERA	European Research Area
ESFRI	European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
GA	OPERAS General Assembly
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MLE	Mutual Learning Exercise
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NN	OPERAS National Nodes. Institutions representing OPERAS AISBL in their respective countries

OA	Open Access
OAeBU	OA Book Usage Data Trust
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OPERAS	Short for OPERAS Research Infrastructure
OPERAS AISBL	Legal structure incorporated in Belgium and coordinating OPERAS
OPERAS Central Hub	OPERAS AISBL + OCT
OPERAS Core Members	Organisations committing to manage the development of OPERAS are engaged in the Executive Assembly, they are also in charge of the national nodes
OPERAS Ordinary Members	Members of this community committing to participate in OPERAS' activities are engaged in the Assembly of the Commons
OPERAS Research Infrastructure	OPERAS Central Hub + OPERAS National Nodes
OPERAS National Nodes	Institutions representing OPERAS AISBL in their respective countries
OPERAS Supporting Member	European and International infrastructures committing to support the development of OPERAS are engaged in the General Assembly next to the Ministry representatives from the countries represented in the Executive Assembly
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area Project
POSI	The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure
RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)
SAC	Scientific Advisory Committee
SIG(s)	Special Interest Groups
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

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Executive summary

This report covers the activities of each of the tasks in OPERAS PLUS Work Package 3: Member States and Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders engagement covering the reporting period September 2022 - December 2023 inclusive.

As part of the ESFRI Roadmap application, OPERAS emphasised the need to grow its membership base across the ERA. This included expansion of Ordinary Members and a particular emphasis on the need to increase core membership from ERA countries in order to increase geographical equity. During the period of this report, six new Ordinary Members were welcomed to the OPERAS community (totalling 47 Ordinary Members). The OPERAS Executive Assembly (EA) also received three new Core Members, which expanded the EA to 13 countries. Furthermore, a new Supporting Member also joined the General Assembly.

As OPERAS grows, so does the need to create efficient and effective lines of communication to ensure that all members get the most out of the OPERAS community and that the OPERAS governance structure continues to work at the optimum level. Therefore, this report outlines OPERAS internal support to the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), Special Interest Groups (SIGs), Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), General Assembly (GA) and Executive Assembly (EA).

During the reporting period, there were three Assembly of the Commons (AoC) meetings, which achieved a milestone for the project. The first AoC, held in September 2022, presented the OPERAS Strategic Plan to the community. The second meeting in April 2023 focussed on the annual Implementation Plan and invited contributions and feedback from the OPERAS community. During the May 2023 meeting, the SIGs presented their current and planned work and highlighted how their objectives and activities are aligned with OPERAS Implementation Plan.

Special Interest Groups (SIGs) comprise the AoC. During the reporting period, the SIG roadmap was introduced as a light touch planning process. As well as detailing SIGs objectives, it also aids the SIGs in aligning their objectives and activities with OPERAS' strategies and ongoing projects, and allows them to better identify their needs and, as a consequence, OPERAS' OCT is able to provide better support.

The roadmap and regular coordination meetings have proved to be helpful for SIG coordinators to identify opportunities for collaboration between SIGs and ongoing projects. It has helped as a tool to identify communication needs and other kinds of support.

Mutual Learning Exercises (MLEs) were established alongside the SIG roadmap. Two sessions were organised, session 1 focused on "How to develop an idea into a new

service or a funded project” and was led by the Multilingualism SIG. Session 2 was dedicated to “Ways of creating and engaging a community”, led by the Open Access Books Network SIG.

There are two key challenges facing the internal operation of the AoC and SIGs. The first relates to the management of the workload for the SIG coordinators. The coordination meetings, roadmap and mutual learning exercises help in this direction. Furthermore, the practice of co-chairing SIGs is being implemented as standard. The second challenge is to ensure an effective participation of the members, such as regular attendance at meetings, active contribution to the roadmap, and having a proactive attitude. A number of initiatives were introduced by SIGs and these will be further developed during the next reporting period.

The Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) of OPERAS has been actively engaged in various discussions and planning sessions throughout 2022 and 2023 via monthly online meetings. In summary, the SAC discussed a range of internal processes, strategic collaborations, and technical recommendations in support of OPERAS' objectives and the outcomes of the Toluca conference and the propositions shared in the Diamond Open Access (OA) discussion paper. A number of external speakers were also invited to various SAC meetings to share their perspectives and projects. In addition an OPERAS's position paper and a SIG white paper were also presented to the SAC for review and comment.

Noteworthy challenges were identified, particularly revolving around the turnover within the SAC. A decision was made to kickstart an open call aimed at candidates with expertise in specific predefined topics through a gap analysis conducted by SAC members.

The General Assembly (GA), OPERAS' highest decision-making body, discussed a number of issues surrounding the transition of OPERAS to an ERIC. This included the unanimous approval of the creation of a Board of Governing Representatives (BGR). The BGR has a strategic focus on legal, governance, and financial matters related to ERIC establishment. Importantly, the BGR is positioned as an independent and transitional body necessary to foster the building of OPERAS ERIC.

The OPERAS Executive Assembly (EA) comprises core members of OPERAS. During the reporting period, a number of key decisions were taken by the EA. These include: adoption of new OPERAS members, votes on Statutes changes, approval of past and planned budgets and fiscal sponsorship, GA meeting agendas and strategies regarding related discussions with ministries, approval of the OPERAS transition governance model, assessing OPERAS AISBL against the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI), and approval to join various external initiatives.

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In response to growing membership of the EA and the wider evolving landscape, a number of improvements have been made to enhance operational efficiency of the EA. This includes general improvement to communications, such as email headers, an internal newsletter and a dashboard giving an overview of pertinent information. Furthermore the EA monthly meeting has been extended to 2.5 hours and follows a more structured approach, which introduces standing items on other OPERAS' bodies in order to ensure effective two-way communication.

An updated report on the activities of OPERAS bodies will be delivered in month 33 of the project (May 2025). It will include an account of the major activities within the work package tasks covering the second reporting period of the project (January 2024–April 2025). It will also reflect on the opportunities and perspectives outlined in this report. Both reports will feed into the creation of a Dashboard of activities of the OPERAS bodies and assemblies. This will be delivered in the final month of the project (August 2025).

I. Introduction

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area. Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

The OPERAS AISBL was established in 2020 with a working governance model that is closely related to the strategic development of OPERAS as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). Building the ERIC implies having Member States at the level of the General Assembly.

As part of the ESFRI Roadmap application, OPERAS emphasised the need to grow its membership base across the ERA. This included expansion of Ordinary Members and a particular emphasis on the need to increase core membership from ERA countries in order to increase geographical equity.

In September 2022, at the start of the OPERAS PLUS project, OPERAS ordinary membership stood at 41 with 10 member states (Core Members) and three Supporting Members (see Figure 1).

During the period of this report, six new Ordinary members were welcomed to the OPERAS community (totalling 47 Ordinary Members):

- Université de Lorraine (France)
- Presses Universitaires de Rennes (France)
- University of Abertay (UK)
- Thoth (UK)

- University of Cyprus Library (Cyprus)
- Spanish National Research Council - CSIC (Spain)

The OPERAS Executive Assembly also received three new Core members, which expanded the EA to 13 countries:

- Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology – FEYCT (Spain)
- ERIH + (Norway)
- Federation of Finnish Learned Societies – TSV (Finland)

Furthermore, a new Supporting Member also joined the General Assembly:

- University Paris-Nanterre (France)

This resulted in a larger Executive Assembly, an increased membership of OPERAS' SIGs and a growing number of new members to bring up to speed with OPERAS' processes and opportunities.

Membership is expected to increase with a number of new members in the pipeline for 2024. As OPERAS grows, so does the need to create efficient and effective lines of communication to ensure that all members get the most out of the OPERAS community and that the OPERAS governance structure continues to work at the optimum level.

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Figure 1. OPERAS' membership in the ERA by country (September 2022).

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1. Ensure an effective engagement with and involvement of all members of OPERAS community across the different groups and bodies of the infrastructure, including ministry representation
2. Monitor and assess the quality and efficiency of internal communication channels, coordination bodies and engagement activities

3. Coordinate the different internal groups of OPERAS, support cross-participation and alignment of their objectives and methods.

Each task report includes a 'challenges and lessons learned' sub-section where issues and opportunities and perspectives are discussed. This allows reflection on the different communication methods required for each stakeholder.

The sections conclude with a number of opportunities and perspectives to take forward in the second half of the project. An updated report on the activities of OPERAS bodies will be delivered in month 33 of the project (May 2025). Both reports will feed into the creation of a Dashboard of activities of the OPERAS bodies and assemblies, which will be delivered in the final month of the project (August 2025).

II. Governance schema

A. Presentation of the governance

In order to report on the actions taken to promote effective engagement and communication within and between the OPERAS community, it is essential to explain the governance of OPERAS AISBL and the roles of the different internal stakeholders.

The OPERAS AISBL governance scheme manages the different levels of engagement of the different types of stakeholders in the development of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure (OPERAS RI) (Figure 2). The community committing to participate in OPERAS' activities is engaged as 'ordinary members' in the Assembly of the Commons. Organisations committing to manage the development of OPERAS are engaged as Core Members in the Executive Assembly. European and international infrastructures committing to support the development of OPERAS are engaged as 'supporting members' in the General Assembly.

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Governance Structure

Figure 2. OPERAS Governance Structure

B. Support to the governance: the role of the Coordination Team

The OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT) acts as the Secretariat of OPERAS RI. It is a composite team of employees from OPERAS AISBL and EA members. In both cases, staff hold either permanent contracts or are employed as part of project work.

The OCT provides a variety of different coordination, management and secretariat functions for the OPERAS RI to support and advise the Executive Assembly and the different bodies of OPERAS. It gathers a variety of expertise and knowledge to support the building of OPERAS as an ERIC in areas such as: strategy and policy; legal and financial; community and communication; service management and technical coordination; National Nodes; and project management and planning.

III. Assembly of the Commons and Special Interest Groups

The [Assembly of the Commons](#) (AoC) is one of OPERAS' governance bodies although it does not have a decisional role. It gathers all Ordinary Members of the infrastructure and it is convened at least once a year. Currently, the objective of the meeting is to present to the Ordinary Members the work completed in the Special Interest Groups over the course of the previous year, propose subjects to be discussed during the General Assembly, and elect the community representatives every two years.

OPERAS [Special Interest Groups](#) (SIGs) work collaboratively, share information, watch, and prepare projects on their topics. Each SIG works under the responsibility of one or more contact points who represent an OPERAS core member. Every ordinary member has to join at least one of the SIGs. In this regard, SIGs serve as an entry door for new OPERAS members. However, any OPERAS member (of any type) can join any SIG and the SIG coordinators can also invite people to participate. This facilitates internal communication flow between the various governance groups within OPERAS.

Internal communication between the various OPERAS groups is key to the development of OPERAS as a mature RI. In the reporting period September 2022 - December 2023, Task 3.1 (Support to the Special Interest Groups and the Assembly of Commons) developed activities aimed at contributing to the achievement of the work package's global objective on internal communication. The OPERAS' community manager leads this task and is responsible for the coordination of both the AoC and SIGs.

To ensure stakeholder engagement of the members at this level, the task has organised AoC meetings, established a plan of activities for the SIGs (in the form of a roadmap), and developed a toolkit of activities for the SIGs through Mutual Learning Exercises. New onboarding procedures to welcome new members and ease their integration into OPERAS activities have also been implemented.

To coordinate and support the participation of the members, the task has contributed to a better alignment between the SIGs activities and OPERAS strategy. It also aimed at increasing OPERAS membership and improving the relation between the SIGs and the Executive Assembly.

These tasks and activities are described in Figure 3 as a number of overlapping objectives. As can be seen, some of the tasks contribute to both ensuring engagement and coordinating activities. Such activities focus on communication and on the articulation between the SIGs and OPERAS nodes and services. Finally, all these activities are monitored through feedback from the AoC and from the SIGs coordinators.

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Figure 3: List of objectives for Task 3.1.

A. **Activities**

1. **Assembly of the Commons**

The AoC elects two co-chairs from the Ordinary Members. The chairs have a seat in the General Assembly. Organising regular AoC meetings contributes to increasing the engagement of OPERAS Ordinary Members by informing them of current activities and projects within OPERAS. AoC members are also asked to give input and feedback. The AoC suggestions are presented to the Executive Assembly (the body responsible for making the decisions).

a. **Meetings**

During the reporting period, there were three AoC meetings, which achieved a milestone for the project. The first AoC was held in September 2022, two others were held in April and May 2023.

The purpose of the first Assembly of the Commons was to present the OPERAS Strategic Plan to the community, followed by a discussion. The second meeting focussed on the annual Implementation Plan and invited contributions and feedback from the OPERAS community. Throughout these two meetings, the OPERAS ordinary members had the opportunity to learn more about OPERAS strategy for the following years but also to be included in the process. During the May 2023 meeting, the SIGs presented their current and planned work and highlighted how their objectives and

activities are aligned with OPERAS Implementation Plan.

The members participation in the AoC is one of the KPIs of the OPERAS PLUS project and is part of the monitoring activities. Around 40% of the Ordinary Members were represented in each of the Assembly of the Commons. One of the challenges for the next reporting period is to increase the participation of the members.

The next Assembly of the Commons will take place as a face to face meeting during the OPERAS Conference April 2024 in Zadar.

2. Special Interest Groups

There are currently seven Special Interest Groups. Figure 4 shows the SIGs and their respective coordinators. All the SIGs have their respective page on OPERAS [website](#).

Figure 4. OPERAS' Special Interest Groups

In relation to OPERAS' Governance, the Special Interest Groups comprise the Assembly of the Commons. The SIGs are an important part of the OPERAS engine. Due to their nature, the SIGs are the groups capable of identifying needs and challenges coming from the broader community. Such needs and challenges can then be addressed by OPERAS through projects and the development of new

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services. Finally, the SIGs represent a forum to produce feedback and to assess if OPERAS activities meet the needs of the community.

a. **Roadmap**

The roadmap is a light touch planning tool formally implemented during the course of the OPERAS PLUS project. It is a template that introduces a planning process for SIGs to use as part of their yearly activities. It gives a framework for the groups while allowing them to maintain their specificities. As well as detailing the SIGs objectives, it also guides the SIGs in how to align their objectives and activities with OPERAS' strategies, methods, and ongoing projects. It is important to note that the roadmap is nonbinding due to the voluntary nature of SIG participation.

Once completed, each template is combined to create the roadmap, which is then shared with the SIGs. This process provides SIGs with the opportunity to track crossovers between the different Groups and to identify ways of collaboration. It allows the groups to better identify their needs and, as a consequence, OPERAS' OCT is able to provide better support.

The SIGs use the roadmap to plan their activities throughout the academic year (September to July). A series of quarterly meetings chaired by OPERAS' Community Manager accompany the coordinators of the SIGs in the process of establishing the roadmap, exchanging their experiences, and monitoring the activities. The first meeting is dedicated to discussion about the new roadmap and the establishment of common objectives of the year. The second and third focus on the draft objectives and the development of different activities, such as the organisation of mutual learning exercises (see below) and AoC meetings. The final meeting allows for a moment of informal reflection where the SIGs coordinators can self-assess the work done and identify challenges and opportunities. These SIG coordination meetings are reported to the Executive Assembly.

The roadmap has two main sections: a general section meant for all the SIGs and a specific one dedicated to each of the groups. The general objectives are based on the list of activities displayed on Figure 3. They include the preparation of the AoC meeting (where the groups will present the work of the year), the organisation of mutual learning exercises (depending on the current needs of the groups), and focus on other actions that might vary each year. Besides the regular activities, such as the AoC meeting, the other objectives are decided by the Community Manager and the SIG coordinators according to specific needs and the capacity to seize opportunities and address challenges.

The second section is an amalgamation of the completed templates where each SIG presents their objective for the year, describing how this objective aligns with OPERAS' strategies, projects and methods. It is an exercise that helps the SIGs

coordinators and participants to clearly identify how their activities are integrated in the OPERAS framework. This section also allows SIG coordinators to reflect on any support that might be required from OPERAS bodies, such as the Executive Assembly for strategic issues, the Scientific Advisory Committee for critical comment and open peer review, or from the Communication Officer for the external amplification of results.

A summary of the work carried out in the academic year of 2022–2023 can be seen below.

First roadmap from 2022–2023

General objectives (to be achieved by all the SIGs as a whole):

- Introducing the practice of having a yearly roadmap that includes a plan of activities for the Special Interest Groups and that takes into account OPERAS Strategic Plan
- Establishing a communication plan for the Special Interest Groups
- Beginning the development of a toolbox of activities to be carried out by the Special Interest Groups through a Mutual Learning Exercise
- Organising one Assembly of the Commons (MS4.1) and providing feedback of the activity.

Specific activities detailed by the different SIGs in the reporting period September 2022 - December 2023 are detailed below. Many of these activities helped to strengthen engagement and communication between and within the SIGs.

- The **Advocacy Special Interest Group** organised an [Open Chat Series](#) with experts in advocacy and communications, researchers, publishers and other members of the SSH community. The series highlighted the connection of the SIG with OPERAS services, such as [Go Triple](#) and the [Innovation Lab](#). The series received some general communication support to advertise the events from the OCT
- The **Best Practices Special Interest Group** defined their modus operandi of contribution and collaboration primarily with the Horizon Europe funded [DIAMAS project](#). The SIG participants represented the OPERAS community as experts in best practices and provided feedback on the first version of the [Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing](#) (EQSIP), an output of the DIAMAS project
- The **Common Standards and FAIR Principles Special Interest Group** offered training to publishers to improve the quality of their metadata and to comply with FAIR requirements in collaboration with CO-OPERAS IN Project. Part of the content of the training was published in two blog posts ([1](#) and [2](#)) and the presentation can be found on [Zenodo](#).

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- The **Multilingualism Special Interest Group** focused on providing input and helpful criticism pertaining to the making of the deliverable of Task 5.5 of the OPERAS-PUS project: D5.5, '[Design components architecture to support the translation platform](#)'. The group gave feedback about the implementation of OPERAS national nodes, in which multilingualism plays an important distinguishing role
- The **Open Access Books Network Special Interest Group** published [blog posts](#) and continued with their programme of events on topics relevant to the OA books community, including participating in the 'How-to-advocacy' open chat series for the Advocacy SIG. They also collaborated with the Horizon Europe funded PALOMERA project by engaging in outreach and validation of the research as part of the ongoing [Palomera Series](#) of events.
- The **Open Access Business Models Special Interest Group** published the second version of the OA Business Models White Paper [Collaborative models for OA book publishers](#) and related anonymized dataset. They presented the paper to OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee for post publication peer review. This paper was also adapted into a Polish language workshop for the OPERAS PL National Node - an example of how internal communication can crossover to National Nodes as well as between SIGs (to be discussed in detail in the next report). They also introduced a new activity, 'News and Newsworthy' to SIG meetings aimed at knowledge exchange and community building within the SIG
- The **Tools and Platforms Special Interest Group** built upon the recommendations of the [White Paper V2](#) (July 2021) by working on an extensive and detailed list of publishing tools. Concretely, the objective is to prepare the creation of a wiki to reuse the contents from the White Paper and through possible collaborations with existing catalogues.

Second roadmap from 2023–2024

The practice of having a roadmap is still being established as part of the OPERAS PLUS project; therefore it is an objective in itself until it is fully consolidated. However, during the reporting period, the SIGs have prepared a second version of the roadmap for 2023/24. Most of the general objectives are unchanged. However, as OPERAS National Nodes are being established through Work Package 7 of the project, the community manager and SIG coordinators decided to focus on strengthening the relations between the SIGs and the nodes. As the OPERAS community grows, another pressing issue that has to be considered as part of the roadmap is how to ensure participation in the SIGs, whether through increasing engagement of existing members or through bringing new members to OPERAS.

General objectives in the second roadmap are to:

- Update the yearly roadmap
- Identify communication needs for the Special Interest Groups and establish an articulation with the different OPERAS bodies
- Continue the development of a toolbox of activities to be carried out by the Special Interest Groups through Mutual Learning Exercises
- Prepare at least one Assembly of the Commons
- Prepare a contribution to the OPERAS 2024 Conference
- Improve the mutual support between the SIGs and the National Nodes
- Increase the number of members and engagement of participants
- Improve the mutual support between the SIGs and the Executive Assembly

The second roadmap was finalised in a SIG Leaders meeting in December 2023. The objectives and individual achievements of the SIGs will be discussed in the next version of the report on activities of OPERAS bodies project deliverable in 2025.

Partial Results

The roadmap has proven to be a helpful document as it became the place where the SIGs can establish their goals and the methods to achieve them. SIG coordinators are able to identify opportunities of building bridges between their activities and the ongoing projects. It has helped as a tool to identify communication needs and other kinds of support. The roadmap and the regular coordination meetings have also been useful to foster the collaboration between the SIGs.

These two management tools allow SIG coordinators to identify similar objectives leading them to work together. By sharing methods employed and actions taken SIG coordinators can indirectly give ideas to the others. Discussions about challenges can lead to collaborative solutions. In other words, this way of managing the SIGs favours crosspollination between the groups. Finally, some OPERAS members participate in different SIGs making the cooperation easier. Below there are two examples of collaboration.

- The Open Access Books Network and Open Access Business Models SIGs started a collaboration to survey and report on smaller OA publisher costs and revenue for books. A working group was established, which included representation from both SIGs and links to other projects such as DIAMAS and PALOMERA were identified
- The Open Access Business Models and Best Practices SIGs held a joint meeting to plan collaboration activities in support of the DIAMAS project. Both SIGs

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agreed to collaborate in reviewing the EQSIP V2 documents, as a result, the SIGs will participate in DIAMAS focus groups in January 2025.

Regarding the update of the roadmap, the SIGs coordinators were in agreement in the final meeting of 2023 that this second exercise was easier and it is getting more accurate as the activities of the groups are better articulated with the activities within different projects. The participants have been showing more engagement in the construction of the roadmap by giving their input. However, they still rely on the coordinators where it comes to the global strategy. This may represent a challenge for the future.

b. *Mutual Learning Exercises*

The development of the toolkit of activities is taking the form of Mutual Learning Exercises (MLE). The MLE allows the construction of new knowledge while facilitating the exchange of information, experiences and lessons learned in practice. Its initial objective was the exchange between the different SIGs (both coordinators and participants) aiming at the collective construction of solutions and an increase of the repertoire of methods and strategies of each of the participants.

Within the first version of the roadmap, two MLE sessions were organised. Following a similar structure, session 1 focused on “How to develop an idea into a new service or a funded project” and was led by the Multilingualism SIG. This SIG had already developed an idea of a translation platform (developed in WP5). It was felt that their experience would benefit other SIGs intending to do the same, i.e., to further develop an idea into a new service or a funded project. The session started with a presentation of the role of the SIGs in the OPERAS RI, followed by a presentation of OPERAS services portfolio. The Multilingualism SIG shared their experience, challenges faced and perspectives for the session. An open conversation concluded the session.

Session 2 was dedicated to “Ways of creating and engaging a community”. The session was led by the Open Access Books Network SIG, due to their experience on the subject matter. This session started with the presentation of this SIG, their practices, challenges faced and perspectives for the future. This was followed by a presentation of the communication and outreach activities in OPERAS, and how OPERAS can support this kind of task. Once again, an open conversation between the participants wrapped up the event.

Within the second roadmap (2023–2024) a new MLE will be organised. It will also be opened up to a larger audience.

3. Engagement and Communication

a. *Onboarding new members and engagement*

With an expanding membership, there are potential risks to internal engagement as SIGs expand. In order to ensure effective engagement of OPERAS members, task 3.1 established new procedures for onboarding new members and conducted some follow up actions to maintain engagement.

Regarding new member onboarding procedures, a welcoming meeting was introduced to better present OPERAS to its new members and to answer questions. It was hoped that this more personal session after application approval would contribute to greater engagement from the outset. This was then extended to the new Core Members as well. During the period of this report, six new ordinary members and three Core Members were welcomed to the OPERAS community (See Introduction).

One of the follow-up actions was aimed at maintaining the engagement of the participants. As part of an update of the SIGs web pages, each SIG provided a list of participants with their respective biographies. As well as acknowledging the contribution of individual SIG members, it is a useful mechanism for SIG coordinators to check-in with SIG members to confirm their participation. The web pages are now updated once a year by the OPERAS Community Manager following the update of the roadmap and this includes confirmation of SIG membership. It gives the coordinators an opportunity to confirm the participation of the members.

b. Communication

Related to work on the SIG web pages and member biographies, new mailing lists were set up for each SIG to facilitate better communication within the different groups. The community is also encouraged to use OPERAS Mattermost installation for more informal communication and information sharing. SIGs will have their own channels and new channels will be created for the community as required.

B. Challenges and lessons learned

There are two key challenges facing the internal operation of the AoC and SIGs. The first relates to the management of the workload for the SIG coordinators. Core Members offer 0.2FTE as an in-kind contribution to OPERAS. This includes membership of the EA, attendance at GA and BGR meetings, as well as the coordination of a SIG. As OPERAS membership grows, so do the demands on Core Members' time.

The coordination meetings, roadmap and mutual learning exercises represent some help in this direction. Furthermore, the practice of co-chairing SIGs is being implemented as standard. Co-chairing can be done by two Core Members or by the coordinator and another participant of the group. This practice has shown to be an opportunity to motivate new Core Members to take new responsibilities in OPERAS

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and to value the engagement of participants. Currently, five of the seven SIGs are co-chaired.

The second challenge is to ensure an effective participation of the members. This includes regular attendance at meetings, active contribution to the roadmap, and having a proactive attitude. Further ideas will be identified and developed during the next reporting period to increase participation of the members. For example, internal satisfaction surveys and 'temperature checks' (as carried out by some of the SIGs); new ways of chairing meetings, such as a rotation of chairs and presenters; inclusion of new activities during the meetings, such as 'news and newsworthy' to encourage new ideas.

It is important to emphasise that most of the actions carried out and described in this report are an opportunity to answer to challenges faced and these will be further reported in the next version of this report.

C. Opportunities and perspectives

Assembly of the Commons

In 2024, the OPERAS Conference will be a major opportunity to have a face-to-face meeting with the Assembly of the Commons and to further strengthen engagement between Ordinary Members, the SIGs and the wider OPERAS community.

Special Interest Groups

The second roadmap brings an opportunity to further develop the general objectives of the SIGs. Although most general objectives remain unchanged, new objectives will open new perspectives on engagement:

- Strengthening the relations between the SIGs and the nodes
- Ensure participation in the SIGs, whether through increasing engagement of existing members or through bringing new members to OPERAS.

In addition to offering mechanisms to support the SIG coordinators in managing the workload, the OPERAS-PLUS project also allows the identification and the testing of new ideas to increase participation of the members.

Regarding communication, it is expected that the new mailing lists and Mattermost channels will encourage interaction amongst members.

IV. Scientific Advisory Committee

The OPERAS [Scientific Advisory Committee](#) (SAC) is an independent body, composed of a number of experts, providing advice and recommendations to the Executive Assembly on the ethical, scientific and technical area for current and future projects as well as OPERAS activities. The SAC was supported in 2023 by one of the two co-coordinators of OPERAS for the logistics and communication with the other bodies

of OPERAS.

The Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) of OPERAS has been actively engaged in various discussions and planning sessions throughout 2022 and 2023. This section of the report provides a comprehensive overview of the key activities and decisions taken during this period.

A. Activities

Throughout the reporting period, the SAC scheduled monthly online meetings, their key activities are grouped below.

A discussion on the plan for OPERAS PLUS Task 3.3 – Support to the Scientific Advisory Committee took place in this period and a blueprint was prepared regarding the OPERAS SAC members' engagement strategy for 2022–2023.

Additionally, during this period, Elea Gimenez Toledo (Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)) was elected as the new co-chair of the SAC in addition to Jean-Claude Guédon (Honorary Professor, Université de Montréal).

During the reporting period, an open question was raised regarding the replacement of two SAC members who stepped down. In a follow up meeting, the SAC identified the need for gap analysis work for potential new SAC positions to ensure appropriate balance of gender, geography and technical expertise.

January face-to-face meeting in Brussels

This meeting focussed on a range of internal processes, strategic collaborations, and technical recommendations as the SAC actively engaged in planning to support OPERAS' objectives. Key points were improved communication within OPERAS bodies, effective SAC contributions to OPERAS objectives, and potential collaboration with the European Commission on terminology and translation. Specific discussions on GoTriple and the OPERAS strategic plan took place during the meeting. One of the SAC members was able to present his work on Multimedia automatic processing techniques and how they could be exploited in a scholarly communication context, opening a path to explore further research and development collaboration with OPERAS.

March online meeting

The SAC discussed and reviewed a position paper prepared by Suzanne Dumouchel as Coordinator for OPERAS RI, "Supporting European capacities for Social Sciences and Humanities academic publishing and scholarly communication: the role of OPERAS Research Infrastructure".

April online meeting

The issue of multilingualism in scientific communication was examined in connection

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with challenges such as terminology, translation technologies, and the discoverability of academic content. Two experts joined the discussion to share their perspectives and projects. Almudena Fernandez from the European Commission's General Directorate of Translation discussed "Terminology work in the Spanish Department (DGT/EC)," while Susanna Fiorini from Université Sorbonne Nouvelle presented on "Translations and Open Science," exploring the role of translation technologies in supporting multilingualism in scholarly communication.

May online meeting

In 2023, the OA Business Models SIG published a white paper after conducting a survey with 74 publishers. The study aimed to enhance understanding of the scholarly publishing landscape for OA monographs and identify trends in collaborative funding and infrastructure models in Social Sciences and the Humanities. Key findings were grouped into three areas: collaboration, funding, and support. The SAC had a presentation of the paper and was invited to comment on it.

June online meeting

Invitations were extended to Kathleen Shearer from COAR to present the Notify Initiative to the SAC. The COAR Notify Initiative is developing and accelerating community adoption of a standard, interoperable, and decentralised approach (using Linked Data Notifications) to link research outputs hosted in the distributed network of repositories with resources from external services, such as overlay-journals and open peer review services.

July online meeting

Plans for the 2023/24 agenda were discussed, in particular in the context of the preparation for the Global Diamond summit to be held in Toluca, Mexico in the autumn. Discussions regarding the identification of new positions to be opened in the SAC.

October online meeting (co-chairs and coordinator)

A meeting with the SAC co-chairs took place to prepare the upcoming year and the addition of new members. Plans for a face-to-face meeting towards the end of the year were discussed, potentially linked to a post-Toluca event. Additionally, a meeting for the SAC in Brussels was scheduled. Finally, a decision was made to have the next f2f meeting of the SAC during the OPERAS Conference in Zadar in April 2024.

November and December 2023

The SAC engaged in a detailed discussion regarding the outcomes of the Toluca conference and the propositions shared in the Diamond Open Access (OA) discussion paper: <https://thd.hypotheses.org/296>. This paper likely covered important aspects of Diamond OA, and the SAC members provided valuable insights and feedback to the authors of the paper.

B. Challenges and lessons learned

At the conclusion of the period, the Committee engaged in a collective reflection regarding the structure and frequency of its meetings. A unanimous consensus emerged to maintain the current approach, consisting of brief one-hour monthly meetings supplemented by an extensive annual face-to-face gathering to accommodate the proceedings of the SAC. Noteworthy challenges were identified, particularly revolving around the turnover within the SAC, as a few junior members withdrew from active participation, primarily attributed to the swift progression of their careers.

Given the need to fill vacant positions within the SAC in 2024, a decision was made to kickstart an open call. This call is explicitly aimed at candidates with expertise in specific predefined topics. Through a gap analysis conducted by SAC members, it was determined that the call for participation should focus on recruiting a researcher in humanities and a researcher in Natural Language Processing (NLP). Additionally, two untargeted positions are slated to be opened alongside these specific roles.

C. Opportunities and perspectives

Based on the lessons learned in 2023, the SAC considered that having a monthly online meeting plus one face-to-face meeting is a good format but requires more assistance from OPERAS AISBL in terms of management and logistics. That is why from January 2024, an office assistant will start supporting the organisation of the SAC on top of the already existing involvement of the co-coordinator.

In 2024 the recruitment of new SAC members will be operationalised and two topics were selected to be worked on, under the lead of the two co-chairs of the committee.

V. General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is the highest decision-making body and has the powers expressly granted to it by law or by the Articles of Association, in particular the following:

1. Amendments to the Articles of Association
2. Appointment and dismissal of the Statutory Auditor and the fixing of their remuneration
3. Approval of the budget for the following financial year and of the annual accounts, as well as granting discharge to the Executive Assembly, the Secretary-General and the Statutory Auditor
4. Voluntary dissolution of the Association
5. Exclusion of Members.

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A. Activities

The General Assembly (GA) is currently composed of EU and international infrastructures that commit to supporting the development of OPERAS, ministries (or proxies) corresponding to the countries where the core members are located, and the Chairs of the AoC, elected by their peers to represent the Ordinary Members at the GA. Members of the OCT attend in a supporting role.

1. Meetings

The General Assembly meets twice a year, a 4-hour virtual meeting and a full-day face-to-face meeting. In case of necessity, extraordinary meetings can take place.

The General Assembly is chaired by the Secretary-General, following a decision of the General Assembly in 2022.

2. Topics and activities

The General Assembly serves as the central hub for a diverse range of activities, showcasing a dual nature that encapsulates both formal and dynamic dimensions.

On one hand, the GA engages in the scrutiny of budgets, embodying its role in shaping the financial landscape of the organisation. This formal role underscores the GA's commitment to procedural governance and fiscal responsibility.

On the other hand, the GA is a dynamic forum where scientific inquiry and opportunistic endeavours flourish. It actively participates in the creation of policy briefs, fostering an environment that encourages strategic discussions and innovative problem-solving. The assembly's commitment to addressing challenges is evident in its ability to adapt, demonstrating an opportunist approach to emerging issues.

Finally, the General Assembly serves as a vital consultative body during the crafting of formal documents, adding its expertise and insights to the developmental process, thereby cementing its pivotal role in shaping the organisational narrative.

During the reporting period, following the decision from the Executive Assembly in May 2023 to move towards an ERIC, the unanimous approval of creating a Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) during the June 2023 General Assembly (GA) signifies a pivotal moment. A number of important issues surrounding the transition to an ERIC were discussed by the ministry representatives, these are included in the challenges, opportunities and lessons learned section below.

B. Challenges and lessons learned

In setting up the governance structure of OPERAS, the creation of the EA and GA were an attempt to mirror the structure of an ERIC in order to smooth the transition. However, operational challenges appeared in the current model, particularly the

inability of Member State representatives to discuss the creation of the ERIC due to the current composition of the GA.

The GA, recognising challenges in discussing OPERAS ERIC due to its current composition, triggered the Executive Assembly's efforts in crafting a transitional governance structure. This led to the proposal of a new Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) and of a new membership category: the Mandated Organisation.

The GA emerges as a central force in the proposed transition governance model (2024–2027) for OPERAS. This move aims to enhance the alignment between the governance of OPERAS AISBL and the future ERIC governance schema.

OPERAS AISBL's twin goals – supporting ERIC establishment and developing initial services – necessitate sustained operational costs. The BGR, as outlined in the draft Terms of References, has a strategic focus on legal, governance, and financial matters related to ERIC establishment. Importantly, the BGR is positioned as an independent and transitional body necessary to foster the building of OPERAS ERIC, but not strictly tied to the governance of OPERAS AISBL.

C. Opportunities and perspectives

The proposed creation of a new membership category, Mandated Organisation, underscores the GA's role in aligning strategies between the BGR and OPERAS AISBL. The GA's composition will now include chairs of the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), the Supporting Members, and the Mandated Organisations. The dynamic inclusion of diverse entities emphasises the GA's central role in shaping the association's direction. The GA's responsibility in overseeing the preparation of documents for the BGR and examining hypotheses underscores its strategic importance. The smooth and transparent dialogue between the GA and the BGR is crucial and will be supported both by the EA and the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT).

The creation of the BGR stems from a proposal by the French Ministry, with France envisioned as the host country for OPERAS ERIC. The GA's step-by-step approach, involving votes, in early December 2023, on the BGR's creation and Mandated Organisation status, highlights the GA's careful consideration in the transition process. The addition of Mandated Organisation membership signifies the GA's commitment to maintaining quality and aligning OPERAS' development with member states' needs.

To prepare for ERIC creation, OPERAS aims to shift from project-dependent funding to a more sustainable financial model. The introduction of mandated organisation status involves national contributions based on country GDP. This strategic move underlines the GA's role in steering OPERAS towards a more sustainable and solid development phase, contributing to the long-term sustainability of the Research Infrastructure. The

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GA's central position is pivotal in shaping both the governance and financial aspects of OPERAS.

These challenges and opportunities will be discussed further in the next version of this report.

VI. Executive Assembly

The OPERAS Executive Assembly (EA) comprises organisations that have successfully applied to become Core Members of OPERAS. These organisations have a heightened commitment to the advancement of OPERAS. The EA has a supervisory role over the activities of the OCT. It is constituted by the administrators of the Association who, in turn, present the tasks and accomplishments undertaken to the General Assembly.

The EA assumes the responsibility of overseeing the operations of the AISBL, making pivotal decisions for daily management, which are subsequently executed by the OCT. In addition to their general responsibilities, members of the EA may undertake specific roles pertinent to OPERAS, such as:

1. Establishing and managing their respective National Nodes (NN)
2. Overseeing the administration of a Special Interest Group (SIG)
3. Serving as the representative of OPERAS in distinct initiatives, including but not limited to [COARA](#), [EOSC](#)-Association, and the [SSHOC](#) consortium.

A. Organisation

1. Meetings

The EA meets once a month, virtually and twice a year in face-to-face meetings. For special topics, it can hold extraordinary meetings.

The EA is chaired on a rolling basis. Each of the OPERAS core members chairs the meetings for three months, the incoming chair serves as vice-chair during this period ensuring that there is coverage in case the chair is unavailable. The timetable of chairing responsibilities is noted in the EA agenda.

2. Topics and activities

The Executive Assembly assumes a pivotal administrative role in steering the strategy and development of the AISBL, overseeing crucial aspects such as accounting, statutes, and membership matters. It serves as the primary entity engaged in the ERIC process, playing a key role in both the preparation of relevant documents and interactions with governmental ministries. Furthermore, the EA holds responsibility for the comprehensive management of the Research Infrastructure, including but not

limited to funded projects, Special Interest Groups, National Nodes, the Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), and various services.

On a monthly basis, the EA convenes to deliberate on significant topics and make essential decisions regarding the management of OPERAS activities. These discussions encompass strategic considerations, such as diamond open access activity, relations with [EOSC](#), and involvement with the [SSHOC](#) cluster. Additionally, the EA is actively involved in decision-making processes concerning new members, categorising them as Ordinary, Core, or Supporting based on specific criteria. This multifaceted approach underscores the EA's central role in shaping and guiding the trajectory of OPERAS.

During the reporting period, a number of key decisions were taken by the EA:

- Adoption of new members in OPERAS (see above)
- Vote on the Statutes changes to be submitted at the GA the 4th of December
- Approval of the past budget and planned budget
- Preparation of the agendas of GA meetings and the BGR in January 2024
- Building on the strategy regarding the discussions with ministries
- Selecting an organisation to organise workshops on the future governance of OPERAS ERIC
- Preparation of the strategy regarding diamond open access activity
- Approval of the fiscal sponsorship of [OAeBU](#) project and launch fiscal sponsorship as an OPERAS service
- Approval of the OPERAS transition governance model
- Formal vote regarding OPERAS becoming an ERIC
- Assessing OPERAS AISBL against the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#) (POSI)
- Validate the OPERAS policy brief regarding its positioning in the European SSH ecosystem
- Approval to join the [SSHOC](#) cluster with Maciej Maryl (Polish Core Member) as representative of OPERAS RI
- Approval to join [COARA](#) initiative with Jadranka Stojanovski (part of the Croatian Core Team) as representative of OPERAS RI.

B. Challenges and lessons learned

Since its inception, the EA has demonstrated great efficiency and direction in steering the establishment of the Association as a legal entity (AISBL) and successfully orchestrating the ESFRI application, securing OPERAS' inclusion in the ESFRI roadmap for 2021.

During the reporting period, the EA has experienced growth, expanding from 10 to 13

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members in 2023, a trend set to continue. This enlargement is envisioned as a means to augment the potential and expertise of EA members, fortifying their capacity to support OPERAS activities. However, the burgeoning activity within OPERAS poses challenges for the EA members in maintaining a comprehensive overview of diverse projects and tasks.

In response to the evolving landscape, recent decisions have been taken to fortify the EA's role and refine the selection of topics for discussion. The once familiar landscape of close-knit EA members has shifted with the introduction of newcomers. Therefore, altering the dynamics and collaborative nature of the group is essential. Previously, EA members seamlessly collaborated on tangible projects. However, this has become less feasible with the expansion of OPERAS. The informal nature of the body is gradually transitioning toward more formal procedures, necessitating adaptability.

Despite the efficacy of rolling chairing, challenges emerge concerning the provision of the agenda, primarily driven by the OCT and centred around an escalating number of hot topics. This leaves limited room for customisation based on the expertise and interests of the chairs, which was one of the expected outcomes of setting up the rolling system. Striking a balance between facilitating discussions among EA members and upholding the EA's role in crucial decision-making is imperative.

Several challenges loom, including the imperative to pre-prepare topics and papers to streamline discussions, a task hindered by constraints in time and resources within the OCT and EA members assigned to specific issues. The inundation of diverse emails pertaining to actions, information, and decisions leaves little time for effective management. The application process for Ordinary Members, while typically unproblematic, consumes substantial meeting time. Furthermore, certain topics, such as Special Interest Groups, National Nodes and the Scientific Advisory Committee's activities (see above), face insufficient discussion. This necessitates a proactive approach to address these gaps in discourse.

1. General improvements

To enhance operational efficiency, several decisions have been taken:

1. **Email Management.** In order to streamline communication, a standardised system for email categorisation will be implemented. Specifically, emails requiring specific actions will be clearly labelled with "[Actions Needed]," while those of urgent nature will be marked with "[Urgent]" within square brackets. This systematic approach aims to facilitate the quick identification and prioritisation of tasks associated with incoming emails.
2. **Enhanced Onboarding Process:** Recognising the importance of a seamless integration process for new Executive Assembly (EA) members, dedicated efforts will be made to better prepare for their welcome. The Communication

Manager and the Community Manager spearhead the onboarding process, ensuring that newcomers are provided with comprehensive information and support. This initiative aims to expedite the acclimatisation of new members to the EA's functions and dynamics.

3. Internal Newsletter: The initiation of discussions regarding an internal newsletter signifies a concerted effort to enhance internal communication. This periodic newsletter will serve as a comprehensive update on key developments, initiatives, and noteworthy achievements within the organisation. The aim is to foster a shared understanding of ongoing activities and promote a sense of unity among the EA members.
4. Dashboard Implementation. A comprehensive dashboard will be developed to cater to the specific needs of both Executive Assembly (EA) and General Assembly (GA) members. This digital platform will provide a centralised and accessible overview of pertinent information, ensuring that members can efficiently track and monitor essential aspects of OPERAS' activities. The dashboard will be designed to enhance transparency and facilitate informed decision-making.

2. Improving the EA agendas

In response to the identified challenges, a proactive approach has been devised, introducing a comprehensive yearly and rolling agendas to be piloted from January 2024 onward. This strategic initiative aims to systematically address various topics, ensuring their thorough consideration and facilitating the preparatory efforts of diverse stakeholders. The success of this implementation will be reported in the next report.

The proposed structure of the agenda is as follows:

1. Regular Items: 20 minutes
 - This segment will allocate dedicated time for routine matters concerning National Nodes (NN), the Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), and Special Interest Groups (SIG). This ensures that essential updates and discussions on these aspects are consistently integrated into the agenda (see Table 1)
2. Political and strategic Items: 40 minutes
 - This block is dedicated to discussing political and strategic matters such as Board of Governors' Reports (BGR), General Assembly (GA) updates, engagements with Ministries, and the Strategic Plan. Allocating a

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focused 40-minute session ensures a comprehensive exploration of these critical elements

3. 15 Minutes of Break
 - Recognising the importance of maintaining focus and fostering productive discussions, a 15-minute comfort break is incorporated into the agenda
4. Administrative, Legal, and Financial Issues (Prospective new members, projects, etc.): 20 minutes
 - Specific time will be designated for deliberating on administrative, legal, and financial matters, including discussions on new member applications, ongoing projects, and related issues. This ensures that necessary administrative aspects are systematically addressed
5. EA/OCT Task Forces (TFs) Updates: 15 minutes
 - This segment provides a concise update on the progress of task forces involving EA members and potentially the OCT. The allocated 15 minutes aim to efficiently convey relevant information
6. Specific Item Related to OPERAS High Strategy: 40 minutes
 - A dedicated 40-minute block is assigned to delve into specific matters related to OPERAS' high-level strategy, encompassing topics such as [COARA](#), [SSHOC](#), [EOSC](#), diamond open access, ERIC Building etc.

Meetings will be extended by 30 minutes to 2.5 hours to allow for in-depth discussions and strategic considerations.

This structured agenda is envisioned as a mechanism to optimise meeting efficiency, ensuring that critical topics are thoroughly addressed while accommodating the diverse and multifaceted nature of OPERAS' strategic initiatives. The trial period starting in January 2024 will allow for iterative refinement based on practical insights and feedback.

Month	Rolling items
January	SIG
Feb	NN
March	SAC
April	SIG
May	NN

June	Face-to-face meeting (+ GA meeting): <i>mainly for strategic and political discussions/brainstorming</i>
July	SIG
August	<i>No meeting</i>
September	NN
October	SIG
Nov	SAC
December	F2F meeting <i>mainly for strategic and political discussions/brainstorming</i>

Table 1. Rolling agenda items

C. Opportunities and perspectives

Based on the identified challenges, a set of strategic decisions have been formulated to enhance the effectiveness and strategic focus of the Executive Assembly:

1. **Preserving the Influential Role of the EA**
 - Efforts will be made to uphold and strengthen the pivotal role of the EA as a potent governing body for the RI. This will involve ensuring that the EA retains its influential position in guiding the strategic direction of OPERAS
2. **Fostering Consensus and Trust Among EA Members**
 - A concerted emphasis will be placed on maintaining a collaborative and trustful atmosphere within the EA. It is imperative to encourage EA members to continue working together in a consensus-driven manner, fostering a collective and unified approach to decision-making.
3. **Simplifying Procedures for EA Members**
 - To alleviate potential complexities, a commitment will be made to avoid unnecessary procedural intricacies for EA members. Streamlining processes will contribute to a more efficient and agile decision-making framework
4. **Enhancing the Strategic Focus of the EA**
 - A shift toward a more strategic orientation for the EA will be actively pursued. The focus will be redirected from daily operational activities to

high-level strategic considerations, ensuring that the EA's efforts align with overarching organisational goals

5. Maintaining Face-to-Face Meetings and Open Discussions

- Recognizing the value of direct interaction, regular face-to-face meetings will be preserved as a fundamental aspect of EA engagement. Open discussions will be encouraged to promote a collaborative exchange of ideas and insights

6. Establishing Task Forces (TFs) for Specific Topics:

- Task Forces (TFs) will be established to address specific topics such as POSI principles, briefing papers, [EOSC](#) tasks, [COARA](#), etc. These TFs, comprising 2-3 EA members, may collaborate with or without the support of an OCT member. These short-term TFs will be dedicated to non-high strategic topics, with a defined duration to discuss and prepare documents for sharing with the EA members. The goal is to provide well-informed suggestions for decisions or actions, particularly in areas not directly related to administrative, financial, or legal matters

These strategic decisions present the opportunity to reinforce the EA's efficacy, strategic focus, and collaborative ethos, contributing to the continuous improvement of OPERAS' governance structure.

VII. Conclusion

This report describes the activities of each of the tasks in OPERAS-PLUS Work Package 3: Member States and Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders engagement for the reporting period September 2022 - December 2023 inclusive.

The activities of each stakeholder group has evidenced effective engagement with and involvement of all members of OPERAS community across the different groups and bodies of the infrastructure, including ministry representation.

In order to monitor and assess the quality and efficiency of internal communication channels, coordination bodies and engagement activities, each task has reported on the challenges and lessons learned during the reporting period. In particular the AoC, SIGs and EA have proactively addressed issues resulting from a rapidly growing OPERAS community. Internal communication has been strengthened and the community has been involved in the process. The SAC has also strengthened its connection to the OPERAS community via interaction with SIGs and commenting on OPERAS papers, while remaining an independent body. The GA has reacted swiftly to the proposal of a BGR by creating new terms of reference and a transitional governance structure in close liaison with the GA and EA.

The first reporting period also shows that work on coordination between the different internal groups of OPERAS has been initiated. Cross participation between the SAC and SIGs, SIGs and the NNs and between the SIGs themselves is reported, as well as the interactions between the EA, GA and BGR. The second SIG roadmap encourages the alignment of objectives and includes specific objectives for SIGs to coordinate work on joint projects and initiatives.

Each task has built on the lessons learned in the reporting period by outlining opportunities and perspectives. In particular, the OPERAS conference will help to bring the AoC closer together in a face to face meeting, the SIGs will look to increase engagement of members and to strengthen relations with the NNs. The SAC will strengthen its relationship with other OPERAS bodies and benefit from greater support from the OCT. Regarding the GA and the newly created BGR, smooth and transparent dialogue between the GA and the BGR is crucial and this will be supported both by the EA and OCT. Finally, the EA will continue to foster collaboration and trust as new Core Members join in order to maintain the EA in its pivotal strategic role.

An updated report on the activities of OPERAS bodies will be delivered in month 33 of the project (May 2025). It will include an account of the major activities within the work package tasks covering the second reporting period of the project (January 2024–April 2025). It will also reflect on the opportunities and perspectives outlined in this report. Both reports will feed into the creation of a Dashboard of activities of the OPERAS bodies and assemblies. This will be delivered in the final month of the project (August 2025).

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